

Lengthened *ortho*-Di-derivatives of Benzene and their Ring-closure. Part VI.* Synthesis of Hepta- thiodiazines and Triazoles.

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In a previous communication (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 181) the reaction of 1-*o*-aminophenyl-3-arylthiocarbamides with thiocarbimides, carbimides, aldehydes, etc., was described and attention was directed to the behaviour of those compounds towards ring-closing agents. In continuation of this work, it appeared to the author to be a matter of some interest to investigate the action of ω -bromoacetophenone, phosgene, etc., upon 1-*o*-aminophenyl-3-arylthiocarbamides.

1-*o*-Aminophenyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide reacts with ω -bromoacetophenone to yield a compound possessing the composition, $C_{15}H_{13}ON_2SBr$ which can be represented by the formula (I). The reaction takes the following course.

The constitutional formula (I) of the compound is supported by the fact that it is acidic in nature, being soluble in cold dilute alkali and precipitated by acids. It is not desulphurised by red oxide of mercury—which shows that the sulphur atom is present in the

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molecule as a member of the ring (compare Busch, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 304; Guha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1502). That the reaction actually takes the course as indicated above is further confirmed by the fact that a compound identical with compound (I) is obtained by condensing 1-*o*-aminophenyl-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide with ω -bromoacetophenone. The intermediate compound (Ia) could not be isolated and it is surprising how aniline could be eliminated so easily under the present experimental conditions. Bose (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **1**, 53; 1925, **2**, 95) found that the condensation of thiosemicarbazides with ω -bromoacetophenone leads simultaneously to the formation of thiodiazine and thiodiazole derivatives accompanied by the elimination of water and hydrobromic acid. Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 153) also found an analogous reaction with 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazide, with this difference, however, that the reaction, in his case, proceeded only in one direction with the exclusion of the thiodiazole compound. It is, therefore, really interesting to note the different way in which the present reaction is taking place and this very fact brings forth an instance how the presence of groupings in the compounds exerts appreciable influence upon the course of the reactions.

1-*o*-Aminophenyl-3-allylthiocarbamide with ω -bromoacetophenone yields only the compound (II), thus :

1-*o*-Aminophenyl-3-arylthiocarbamide reacts with phosgene to yield a heptathiodiazine derivative, thus :

where R = phenyl, *p*-tolyl, or 1:3:4-xylyl.

(cf. Busch, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1899, ii, 60, 25; Guha and Roy-Choudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 164). The compound (III) is soluble in dilute alkali and does not possess any mercaptanic properties.

By the action of nitrous acid on *l*-*o*-aminophenyl-3-arylthiocarbamide, a triazole derivative is obtained, thus:

where R = phenyl, *p*-tolyl or *m*-tolyl.

(compare Robinson and Thornley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2169). Freund and Schwarz (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2491) obtained, by the action of nitrous acid on thiosemicarbazides, thiotriazole derivatives which evidently contain sulphur in the ring, whereas the present ring-closure is taking place through the nitrogen atom. The compound (IV) is acidic in nature being soluble in cold dilute alkali, is desulphurised by red oxide of mercury and liberate mustard oil on standing for a few hours.

o-Phenylthiocarbamidophenylurethane $\text{EtO}_2\text{C}-\text{NH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{NH}-\text{CS}-\text{NHPh}$ on treatment with 15 per cent. caustic potash solution yields a mixture of *o*-phenylenethiourea (V) and 2-phenylamino-4:5-benzo-1:3-thiazole (VI), thus:

The compound (V) was prepared by Ghosh and Guha (*loc. cit.*). Hofmann (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1796) prepared the compound (VI) by the action of *o*-amidophenylmercaptan on phenylthiocarbimide,

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Phenyl-2-bromomethyl-4:5-benzo-7-ketotetrahydro-1:3:6-heptathiodiazine (I).—An intimate mixture of *l-o*-aminophenyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide (2.5 g.) and ω -bromoacetophenone (2 g.) was boiled with dilute acetic acid (30 c.c.) for about half an hour. The clear dark brown solution, on standing yielded a white solid product which was twice crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m. p. 230° (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.22; S, 8.22; Br, 23.25. $C_{15}H_{13}ON_2SBr$ requires N, 8.02; S, 9.17; Br, 22.92 per cent.) The presence of aniline in the acetic acid solution was confirmed by diazotisation and coupling with β -naphthol. The compound is soluble in cold dilute alkali and is precipitated by acids.

Action of ω -Bromoacetophenone upon l-o-Aminophenyl-3-p-tolylthiocarbamide: Formation of (I).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the compound (I). The product was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m. p. 230° (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.30. $C_{15}H_{13}ON_2SBr$ requires N, 8.02 per cent.). The identity of this compound with the preceding compound was further confirmed by studying its properties which were similar to those of compound (I) and finally by taking the mixed melting point.

2-Phenyl-2-bromomethyl-4:5-benzo-7-allylaminodihydro-1:3:6-heptathiodiazine (II).—An intimate mixture of *l-o*-aminophenyl-3-allylthiocarbamide (2.1 g.) and ω -bromoacetophenone (2 g.) was boiled with acetic acid under reflux for about half an hour. The clear dark brown solution, on standing yielded a white crystalline product which crystallised from acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 201-202°. It is insoluble in cold alkali and is not desulphurised by red oxide of mercury. (Found: N, 10.68; S, 8.63. $C_{18}H_{18}N_3SBr$ requires N, 10.82; S, 8.24 per cent.)

2-Keto-4:5-benzo-7-phenylaminodihydro-1:3:6-heptathiodiazine (III, R = Ph).—*l-o*-Aminophenyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide (2.5 g.) was dissolved in hot dry benzene to which the required quantity of phosgene (20 per cent. in toluene solution) was then added. A semi-solid mass came out and the solution was further boiled on the water-bath for an hour more. The semi-solid mass was purified by dissolving it in dilute caustic soda solution and precipitating by dilute hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m. p. 175-176°. It is not desulphurised by

red oxide of mercury. (Found: N, 15.83. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_3S$ requires N, 15.67 per cent.)

The *monomethyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol in shining colourless hexagonal prisms, m.p. 126-27°. (Found: N, 14.51. $C_{15}H_{13}ON_3S$ requires N, 11.83 per cent.)

2-Keto-4:5-benzo-7-p-tolylaminodihydro-1:3:6 heptathiodiazine (III, R = *p-tolyl*).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the previous compound. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m. p. 184-185°. (Found: N, 14.65. $C_{15}H_{13}ON_3S$ requires N, 14.84 per cent.)

2-Keto-4:5-benzo-7-(1:3:4)xylylaminodihydro-1:3:6-heptathiodiazine (III, R = 1:3:4-*xylyl*).—It crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m. p. 173-174°. (Found: S, 10.49. $C_{16}H_{15}ON_3S$ requires S, 10.77 per cent.)

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from acetic acid in fine colourless needles, m. p. 202-204°.

1-Phenylthiocarbonamido-4:5-benzo-1:2:3-triazole (IV).—An aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (1 g) was allowed to fall slowly from a separating funnel to an acetic acid solution of *l-o*-aminophenyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide (2.5 g.) which was being cooled in a freezing mixture of ice and salt. The solution turned yellow and a yellowish white crystalline substance came out which crystallised from ether in rectangular plates, m. p. 87-88°. It slowly liberates phenyl mustard oil on standing. (Found: N, 22.32; S, 12.31. $C_{13}H_{10}N_4S$ requires N, 22.04; S, 12.59 per cent.)

1-p-Tolylthiocarbonamido-4:5-benzo-1:2:3-triazole (IV, R = *p-tolyl*).—The method of preparation was identical. It was crystallised from ether in yellowish-white rectangular plates, m. p. 115°. (Found: S, 12.08. $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$ requires S, 11.94 per cent.)

l-o-Aminophenyl-3-m-tolylthiocarbamide.—It was prepared according to the method of Lellmann (*Annalen*, 1885, 228, 212) and was crystallised from benzene in shining colourless prisms, m. p. 144°. (Found: N, 16.12. $C_{14}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 16.34 per cent.)

1-m-Tolylthiocarbonamido-4:5-benzo-1:2:3-triazole (IV, R = *m-tolyl*).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the compound (IV). It crystallised from ether in yellowish-white rectangular plates, m. p. 94°. (Found: N, 21.26. $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$ requires N, 20.89 per cent.)

Action of Potassium Hydroxide upon o-Phenylthiocarbamidophenylurethane: Formation of o-Phenylenethiourea (V) and 2-Phenylamino-

4:5-*benzo-1:3-thiazole* (VI).—*o*-Phenylthiocarbamidophenylurethane (5 g.) was heated on the water-bath with an excess of 15% potassium hydroxide solution for about 2 hours. The solution was then diluted with water, cooled and filtered from the white precipitate (VI) which, after being completely washed with hot water, was crystallised from alcohol in shining colourless plates, m. p. 158-159°. (Found: N, 12.34. $C_{13}H_{10}N_2S$ requires N, 12.38 per cent.). The alkaline solution, on acidification, yielded a product (V) which crystallised from hot water acidulated with a few drops of hydrochloric acid in shining colourless prisms, m. p. 301-302°. (Found: N, 18.45. $C_7H_6N_2S$ requires N, 18.66 per cent.). It is soluble in cold dilute alkali and gives a disulphide (m. p. 230°).

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